

METAPHOR AND METONYMY

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Annotation. Each language has its origin, history, and uniqueness. Every language has special words that can make the words you want to say emotional, artistic, exaggerated and emphasize. We call such words metaphor and metonymy. These phrases are familiar to us since school days. It also has its forms and order of occurrence in the structure of the sentence. That's what this article is about, and you can learn more about Metonymy and Metaphor.

Keywords: *metonymy, metaphor, artistic imagination, text, words, phrases, tone, speech.*

Annotatsiya. Har bir tilning kelib chiqishi, tarixi va o‘ziga xosligi bor. Har bir tilda siz aytmoqchi bo‘lgan so‘zlarni hissiy, badiiy, bo‘rttirib, ta’kidlaydigan maxsus so‘zlar mavjud. Bunday so‘zlarni metafora va metonimiya deb ataymiz. Bu iboralar bizga maktab davridan tanish. U gap tarkibida ham o‘ziga xos shakl va yuzaga kelish tartibiga ega. Ushbu maqola aynan shu haqida bo‘lib, siz Metonimiya va metafora haqida ko‘proq bilib olishingiz mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: *metonimiya, metafora, badiiy tasavvur, matn, so‘z, ibora, ohang, nutq.*

Аннотация. Каждый язык имеет свое происхождение, историю и уникальность. В каждом языке есть особые слова, которые могут сделать слова, которые вы хотите сказать, эмоциональными, художественными, преувеличенными и подчеркнутыми. Мы называем такие слова метафорой и метонимией. Эти фразы знакомы нам еще со школьных времен. Оно также имеет свои формы и порядок появления в структуре предложения. Вот о чем эта статья, и вы можете узнать больше о метонимии и метафоре.

Ключевые слова: *метонимия, метафора, художественное воображение, текст, слова, словосочетания, тон, речь.*

INTRODUCTION

Like all languages, the Uzbek language also has types of meaning transfer. They are metaphor, metonymy, simile, irony and synecdoche. The word metaphor is a Greek word derived from the word "metaphor" which means to transfer, copy. A metaphor is a transfer of meaning based on similarity between 2 objects. The transfer of meaning in metaphor is based on 3 things. They are: similarity in form, similarity in character, and last but not least, similarity in action. Metaphor and metonymy are widely used not only in works of art, but also in various aspects of art. Because the only thing that unites all professions is oral speech.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Metaphor is very common in many Uzbek dialects and in common speech. In our speech, they lose their original meaning and have a portable meaning. For example: a person's ear - in this word, the word "ear" is its own meaning. "the ear of the cauldron" - and we can see that it comes in a figurative sense. Let's use the word "cold" in the sentence "Don't think cold, my friend." The word "cold" is used in its own sense for air and water. When the words "cold intention", "cold breath", "cold person" appear in sentences, the word "cold" is used figuratively out of its meaning. In this sentence, "I've had my stomach full for one six", we use the word "six" alone. When the word "six" is used alone, it means six, that is, an iron object, and it not something to eat, this word has two different meanings when it is used alone and in the text, and it is used figuratively in the text. Here we have learned two different meanings of words, native and figurative, and how to find them. Aristotle expresses the following opinion in his work "Rhetoric": "Metaphor has a high degree of accuracy, pleasantness and charm of grace, its appropriate use decorates the speech."

METONYMY.

Metonymy means "meta" again, "anoma" means name. The transfer of meaning that occurs due to the transfer of the name of one to the other from the connection of the object and the subject is called metonymy. Metonymy is the use of a related term to stand for an object or concept. You will find examples of metonymy frequently used both in literature and in everyday speech. You can use it without realizing it. Sometimes metonymy is chosen because it is a well-known feature of the concept. A famous example is: "The pen is mightier than the sword", from Edward Bulwer Lytton's play "Risely". This sentence has two metonyms:

"Pen" means "written word".

"Sword" means "military aggression".

The use of such artistic painting is more convenient for poets and writers. Because they can use such words effectively. Some of the world famous poems and major works also include metaphorical words in order to show how effective they are.

"Friends, Romans, countrymen, listen to me." (Julius Caesar, William Shakespeare).

"Ears" refers to the ability to listen. In fact, Shakespeare is not asking everyone to cut off their ears, he is asking them to listen. In this case, a word with a close meaning, i.e. metonymy, is used. "If metaphor works by transferring qualities from one plane to another, metonymy works by connecting meanings on the same plane. This aspect is the difference between them.

CONCLUSION

It is very difficult to imagine literature and comics without metaphor and metonymy. Many people have forgotten that some words have lost their meaning and are used figuratively. Metaphor and metonymy, known as the main basis of fiction, are still used by many artists. Metonymy is like another literary device. However, they differ in

the principle of value transfer. Metonymy is formed by adjacent or directly related objects—for example, a material instead of the object itself. A metaphor involves events that can be compared. Both serve to make words attractive and effective. Especially metonymy

in order to figuratively express factual evidence, just like history is used. He is the author's comments on the event being described can reveal. An exaggerated, generalized characteristic of a character or phenomenon, when compared to something else, gives information about that other thing.

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